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Olamkicept for IL-6 receptor inhibition in Crohn's Disease.

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We measured total transcription in the blood and in the gastrointestinal tract in two humans treated with olamkicept prior to initiation of treatment and at 2 weeks to identify putative mechanisms of action associated with IL-6R inhibition in humans with Crohn's Disease.

1 Results

2 GSE171770

3 Study design: 2 patients, whole blood, at 0d and 2 weeks (14 days)

4 Figure 1: Olamkicept results in significant reduction in B-cell activity.

- 5
- 6 a. MZB
- 7 1. Marginal zone function
- 8 b. JCHAIN
- 9 c. Immunoglobulin gene segments

10 Figure 2: Markers of homeostasis restoration by IL-6R inhibition.

- 11 a. Txndc5 reduction

12 Figure 3: Compensatory signaling in the blood is a major component of the transcriptional response to olamkicept

- 13 a. IL1RAP induction
- 14 b. TAGAP induction

15 Figure 4: TNFRSF17 is a major target of the IL-6 receptor signaling pathway in the hematopoietic compartment.

- 16
- 17 a. Tnfrsf17 encoding *BCMA* is the receptor for *APRIL* and *BAFF* encoded by TNFSF13 and TNFSF13B.
- 18

19 Figure 5: Genomic instability induced during clinical intervention with olamkicept alludes to compensatory

- 20 a. Tigd3 induction
- 21

22 Study design: 2 patients, GI biopsy, at 0d and 2 weeks (14 days)

23 Figure 6: IL1RN signaling is abolished by olamkicept

24 Figure 7: HCAR2 and HCAR3 silencing resulting from olamkicept administration *in vivo*

- 25 a. A significant metabolic component to the IL6R pathway
- 26

27 Figure 8: Xpnpep2 silencing

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1 Figure 9: Slc15a1 is an olamkicept and/or IL-6 pathway target in the GI tract.

- 2 a. Slc15a1 is a brush border peptide transporter in the intestines.

3
4 Figure 10: Muc5b is a specific target of olamkicept therapeutic function in humans with CD.

- 5 a. Mucin function in the GI tract.

6 Figure 11: Compensatory signaling in the mucosal epithelial tissues of the gastrointestinal tract
7 resulting from administration of olamkicept in humans with CD.

- 8 a. Alox15b induction

9 Figure 12: Significant reduction in a hypoxic tissue response

- 10 i. Elgn3 loss

11 Figure 13: Autophagic change associated with olamkicept inhibition of the iL-6 receptor signaling
12 pathway in humans.

- 13 ii. Depp1 loss.

14 Figure 14: In sum, restoration of homeostasis in the blood (i.e., loss of *TXNDC5*) was associated
15 with therapeutic silencing of IL-1R signaling through *IL1RN* in the gut.

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Citations

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2. Zhang, S., Chen, B., Wang, B., Chen, H., Li, Y., Cao, Q., Zhong, J., Shieh, M.J., Ran, Z., Tang, T. and Yang, M., 2023. Effect of induction therapy with olamkicept vs placebo on clinical response in patients with active ulcerative colitis: a randomized clinical trial. *Jama*, 329(9), pp.725-734.